

Multinuclear Nmr Study of the Reactivity of BCl_3 with (Dimethylamino)dichloroarsine and (Dimethylamino)-dimethylarsine¹

LARRY K. KRANNICH*, RAVINDRA K. KANJOLIA and CHARLES L. WATKINS

Department of Chemistry, University of Alabama at Birmingham, Birmingham, AL 35294, U.S.A.

The reactions of BCl_3 with $\text{Cl}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ and $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ have been carried out and followed by temperature-dependent ^{11}B , ^{13}C , and ^1H nmr. At -100° , $\text{Cl}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ forms $\text{Cl}_2\text{AsNMe}_2\cdot\text{BCl}_3$. Decomposition of this adduct begins within a short time to yield Me_2NBCl_2 and AsCl_3 . At -100° , $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ gives equimolar amounts of the $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2\cdot\text{BCl}_3$ and $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2\cdot\text{BCl}_3$ adducts. The As-B and N-B adducts undergo rearrangement to intermediates that decompose ultimately to a mixture of Me_2NBCl_2 and Me_2AsCl . The reaction of Me_2NBCl_2 with $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ at -90° gives $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2\cdot\text{Me}_2\text{NBCl}_2$ which subsequently decomposes to $(\text{Me}_2\text{N})_2\text{BCl}$ and Me_2AsCl . The nmr spectral data for these reactions and the intermediate reaction products are discussed.

THERE has been considerable interest in the past several years in the relative Lewis acidities of boron trihalides toward selected phosphines, arsines and stibines²⁻¹². However, the reactions of aminophosphines and aminoarsines with boron trihalides have received minimal attention^{4,5,8}. These systems are of interest, because they contain two adjacent Lewis base sites, each of which could participate in bonding with the Lewis acid. Although Holmes and Wagner⁴ investigated the relative base strengths of several dimethylamino-substituted phosphines with BCl_3 and BF_3 , their data were insufficient to establish the initial site of attack of the boron. BF_3 forms a 1:1 N-B bonded adduct with F_2PNMe_2 . Morse and Morse⁸ examined the reaction of Me_2NAsF_2 with BF_3 and established the formation of a N-B bonded adduct, which decomposed to $[\text{Me}_2\text{NBF}_2]_2$ and AsF_3 .

In this paper, we report the reactions of BCl_3 with (dimethylamino)dichloroarsine and (dimethylamino)dimethylarsine and of Me_2NBCl_2 with (dimethylamino)dimethylarsine. The course of each reaction was followed by temperature-dependent ^{11}B , ^{13}C , and ^1H nmr data. The reactions occur at very low temperature. The formation of hitherto unknown 1:1 As-B and N-B bonded addition compounds, pentacoordinate arsenic intermediate products, and the subsequent decomposition reactions are discussed.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of BCl_3 and $\text{Cl}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ in 1:1 molar ratio in toluene- d_6 solution occurs at -100° to give $\text{Cl}_2\text{AsNMe}_2\cdot\text{BCl}_3$. Both dissolved and undissolved adducts (white solid) are present. The temperature-dependent ^{11}B and ^{13}C nmr spectra are shown in Fig. 1. The ^{13}C nmr chemical shift

of the Me_2N carbons in the parent compound (37.84 ppm) is shifted downfield to 43.34 ppm and the ^{11}B nmr chemical shift of the BCl_3 (45.28 ppm) is shifted upfield to 8.69 ppm in the adduct. Broad multiplet peaks at 25.69 and 23.34 ppm are observed in the ^{13}C spectra, but disappear within one hour as the BCl_3 is consumed in the reaction. Within 1 hour at -100° , some decomposition of the adduct begins as evidenced by the appearance of peaks assignable to Me_2NBCl_2 (^{13}C , 38.69; ^{11}B , 29.54 ppm), a new peak at 39.62 ppm and broadening of the 43.34 ppm peak (adduct) in the ^{13}C spectrum, and asymmetry of the 8.69 ppm peak (adduct) and a new peak at 6.73 ppm in the ^{11}B spectrum. As the spectra are monitored at -90 , -80 , and -70° , the 8.69 ppm ^{11}B peak shifts upfield and resolves into two peaks at 8.55 and 8.18 ppm. Over this temperature range, the peak at 8.55 ppm decreases in intensity as that at 29.06 ppm (Me_2NBCl_2) increases, until at -70° the ^{11}B spectrum consists of three peaks: 29.06, 8.18 and 6.73 ppm. In the ^{13}C spectra, these changes are accompanied by a narrowing of the 43.35 ppm peak, appearance of peaks at 48.57 (broad) and 41.26 ppm, and then, at -70° , simplification of the spectrum to three peaks at 43.45, 38.87 and 38.79 ppm. Over a 40 hour period at -70° and then with increasing temperature up to -30° , the spectra remain unchanged. Above -30° , the spectra indicate further decomposition to Me_2NBCl_2 . After 7 hours at 0° , the spectra indicate the presence of Me_2NBCl_2 (^{13}C , 39.15; ^{11}B , 29.33 ppm), a trace of excess BCl_3 , and a trace of another species (^{13}C , 38.83; ^{11}B , 6.66 ppm) that contains the Me_2NB -moiety.

These data suggest the initial formation of a B-N adduct and the existence of two independent reaction pathways to the formation of Me_2NBCl_2 . The one pathway proceeds at -100° and involves the direct decomposition of the adduct to Me_2NBCl_2 . By

Fig. 1. ^{13}C and ^{11}B nmr spectra of the reaction of BCl_3 and $\text{Me}_2\text{NAsCl}_2$: (A) -100° initially, (B) -100° after 2.5 h, (C) -80° after 6 h, (D) -70° after 7 h, (E) -70° after 40 h and (F) 0° after 7 h at 0° .

analogy to the decomposition of $\text{F}_2\text{AsNMe}_2\text{BF}_3$, the other product should be AsCl_3 . Formation of Me_2NBCl_2 via this pathway is completed at -70° as evidenced by the invariance in the spectra with time. At -100° , the data suggest the formation of a more stable rearrangement product (^{13}C , 43.45; ^{11}B , 8.18 ppm) which is stable up to -30° . The nmr data suggest, this intermediate product contains a B-N bond and a tetracoordinate boron. We postulate it to be a pentacoordinate arsenic species where two chlorine atoms and the Me_2N group occupy the equatorial positions and the more electronegative chlorine species preferentially occupy the apical positions^{13,14}. The boron is coordinated to the nitrogen of the Me_2N group and two chlorine atoms on one face of the trigonal bipyramid and bonded to a third chlorine atom to yield a tetracoordinate boron species. Decomposition of this species above -30° provides the second pathway to the formation of Me_2NBCl_2 and AsCl_3 .

A separate nmr study of a solution of 1 mmol of BCl_3 dissolved in 2.5 ml of toluene- d_6 at -100° established that the peaks at 25.69 and 23.34 ppm arise from an association of BCl_3 and toluene at the

melting point of the solution. This association is weak and causes the observed downfield shifts in the toluene Me groups.

The reaction of BCl_3 and $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio in toluene- d_6 solution also occurs at -100° to give an equimolar mixture of $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2\text{BCl}_3$ (^{11}B , 8.06 ppm) and $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNM}_2\text{BCl}_3$ (^{11}B , 4.25 ppm) and some unreacted BCl_3 (44.88 ppm). The temperature-dependent ^{11}B and ^{13}C nmr spectra are shown in Fig. 2. Initially the ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts of the parent Me_2N (42.29 ppm) and Me_2As (9.56 ppm) carbons are unchanged, but are considerably broadened. After 30 minutes, narrowing of the peaks occurs and additional peaks that can be assigned to the N-B and As-B adducts appear in the ^{13}C spectrum. The ^{13}C nmr chemical shift of the Me_2N carbons in the parent compound (42.29 ppm) is shifted downfield to 48.71 ppm (broad) and of the Me_2As carbons is shifted upfield to 9.15 ppm, which suggests an N-B adduct. Simultaneously, peaks assignable to an As-B adduct are observed: upfield shift of the Me_2N carbons to 41.33 ppm and downfield shift of the Me_2As carbons to 19.57 ppm. In addition, peaks at 15.35, 16.66, 23.35, 25.88, 39.64

Fig. 2. ^{13}C and ^{11}B nmr spectra of the reaction of BCl_3 and $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$: (A) -100° initially, (B) -100° after 2 h, (C) -100° after 4 h, (D) -80° after 6.5 h, (E) -60° after 8 h and (F) -20° after 12 h.

and 44.38 ppm appear in the ^{13}C spectra, and at 9.13 and 6.50 ppm appear in the ^{11}B spectra. Within 2.5 hours, the reaction has gone to completion and the BCl_3 toluene adduct peaks (^{13}C , 23.35 and 25.88 ppm) have disappeared. Peaks assignable to the parent aminoarsine in the ^{13}C spectrum and BCl_3 in the ^{11}B spectrum are now absent.

Over a 4 hour period at -100° , significant changes occur in both the ^{13}C and ^{11}B spectra. In addition to the appearance of the new peaks and the reaction having gone to completion, as described above, decomposition of the N-B compound begins to occur after 3 hours. Peaks assigned to the N-B adduct decrease in intensity, as peaks assignable to Me_2NBCl_2 (^{13}C , 38.78; ^{11}B , 29.88 ppm) and Me_2AsCl (^{13}C , 19.58 ppm, broad) increase in intensity. In addition, the peak at 44.38 ppm decreases in intensity; peaks at 39.64, 16.66 and 15.39 ppm disappear; a broad low intensity peak remains at 48.84 ppm; and a peak at 46.82 ppm, appears in the ^{13}C spectrum. The ^1H spectra, although poorly resolved, indicate numerous peaks

in the Me_2N region (2.3 to 1.95 ppm) and at least four peaks in the Me_2As region (1.2 to 0.8 ppm).

As the temperature increases from -100 to -40° , the spectra simplify. In the ^{13}C spectra, the peak at 48.64 ppm narrows, increases in intensity, and then disappears (-40°), and that at 19.53 ppm narrows. In the ^{11}B spectra, the peak at 4.70 ppm shifts downfield and decreases in intensity, that at 8.54 ppm (As-B adduct) disappears as a peak at 9.05 ppm increases in intensity and one at 9.32 ppm becomes identifiable. The ^1H spectra at -80° indicate two types of Me_2As (0.914 and 0.910 ppm) and several types of Me_2N (broad peaks centered at 2.21, 2.13 and 2.08 ppm). As the temperature increases, the peaks at 2.13 disappear and those at 2.21 and 2.08 narrow and begin to merge.

At -20° and above, the ^{13}C spectrum indicates only Me_2NBCl_2 (39.07 ppm), Me_2AsCl (20.07 ppm) and a minor peak at 38.81 ppm. The ^{11}B spectrum shows that Me_2NBCl_2 is the predominant boron containing species. A minor peak at 6.66 ppm is

also present. The ^1H spectrum consists of a peak at 2.23 ppm (Me_2NBCl_2), which shifts downfield to 2.35 ppm at room temperature, and one at 1.03 ppm (Me_2AsCl).

These data suggest the initial formation of N-B and As-B adducts and the existence of several independent reaction pathways to the formation of Me_2NBCl_2 and Me_2AsCl over the studied temperature range. The direct decomposition of the N-B adduct occurs at -100° and is complete within 4 hours. At -100° , the data also suggest the existence of unstable N-B and As-B bonded rearrangement products (N-B: ^{13}C , 48.69, 16.67, and 15.39; ^{11}B , 4.47; As-B: ^{13}C , 44.38 and 19.63; ^{11}B , 9.32 ppm). We postulate these intermediate products to be pentacoordinate arsenic species containing N-B or As-B bonds and tetracoordinate boron. Several structures are possible for the N-B or As-B cases, depending upon the distribution of the Cl, Me and Me_2N moieties among the apical and equatorial positions. Decomposition of these species provides additional pathways to the formation of Me_2NBCl_2 and Me_2AsCl .

A more stable N-B bonded rearrangement product (^{13}C , 46.80, 19.62; ^{11}B , 4.70 ppm) is also observed. This species is stable up to -40° and then decomposes to Me_2NBCl_2 and Me_2AsCl . By analogy to the $\text{Me}_2\text{NAsCl}_2$ reaction, this species should contain the Me_2N moiety, a chlorine and a Me group in the equatorial positions, and a chlorine and the other Me group in the apical position. Decomposition of this intermediate product yields Me_2NBCl_2 and Me_2AsCl .

At -100° , there is no apparent decomposition of the As-B adduct to Me_2NBCl_2 and Me_2AsCl . Instead, over a period of time, the As-B adduct forms a rearrangement product (^{13}C , 41.62 and 19.62; ^{11}B , 9.07; ^1H , in the 0.91 ppm envelope) that contains an As-B bond and tetracoordinate boron and is stable up to -80° . We postulate this to be a pentacoordinate arsenic species. Decomposition of this intermediate product also yields Me_2NBCl_2 and Me_2AsCl .

At room temperature, the spectra suggest the existence of a small amount of N-B bonded compound—an adduct of Me_2AsCl and Me_2NBCl_2 . A temperature-dependent multinuclear nmr study was carried out on a 1:1 molar mixture of Me_2NBCl_2 and Me_2AsCl in toluene- d_6 solution. The spectra indicated the formation of a slight amount of $\text{Me}_2\text{AsCl} \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{NBCl}_2$ (^{13}C , 38.88; ^{11}B , 6.97 ppm) at very low temperature. A temperature-dependent multinuclear nmr study on a 1:1 molar mixture of BCl_3 and Me_2AsCl in toluene- d_6 indicated no bonding interactions under the conditions used in the $\text{BCl}_3/\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ reaction.

The reaction of Me_2NBCl_2 with $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2$ was followed by temperature-dependent ^{11}B , ^{13}C , and ^1H nmr data. The reaction, using a 1:1 molar ratio of reactants in toluene- d_6 solution, occurs at very low temperatures and is complete by -90° .

An adduct, $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{NBCl}_2$, of low solubility is formed, which upon dissolving is in exchange with its decomposition products— Me_2AsCl and $(\text{Me}_2\text{N})_2\text{BCl}$. At -90° , the nmr spectra suggest that the reaction mixture contains the following: Me_2AsCl (^{13}C , 19.59; ^1H , 0.90 ppm), $(\text{Me}_2\text{N})_2\text{BCl}$ (^{13}C , 39.63; ^{11}B , 29.10, broad asymmetric peak; ^1H , 2.39 ppm, broad peak); $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{NBCl}_2$ (^{13}C , 39.62 and 19.59; ^{11}B , 29.10, broad asymmetric peak; ^1H , 2.39, broad peak, and 0.90 ppm); and $[\text{Me}_2\text{NBCl}_2]_2$ (^{13}C , 46.31; ^{11}B , 9.42; ^1H , 2.54 ppm). As the temperature is increased progressively to -10° , the asymmetry of the broad peak (29.10 ppm) in the ^{11}B spectrum disappears and the peak becomes resolved into two peaks— Me_2NBCl_2 (29.25 ppm), which is in slight excess, and $[\text{Me}_2\text{N}]_2\text{BCl}$ (26.84 ppm). The peak at 39.62 ppm in the ^{13}C spectrum becomes resolved into two peaks— $[\text{Me}_2\text{N}]_2\text{BCl}$ (39.74 ppm) and $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{NBCl}_2$ (39.56 ppm). The peaks at 2.391 and 0.90 ppm in the ^1H spectrum shift downfield to 2.48 and 1.08 ppm, respectively, with considerable narrowing of line width. The line widths and intensities of peaks in the ^{13}C and ^{11}B spectra associated with Me_2AsCl , $[\text{Me}_2\text{N}]_2\text{BCl}$, and $\text{Me}_2\text{AsNMe}_2 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{NBCl}_2$ suggest that exchange is occurring in solution with rapid conversion of the adduct to Me_2AsCl and $[\text{Me}_2\text{N}]_2\text{BCl}$ as solubility increases with increasing temperature. At room temperature, the sample consists of a mixture of Me_2AsCl and $[\text{Me}_2\text{N}]_2\text{BCl}$.

Currently we are extending the above investigations by studying the reactions of boron halides and mixed halides with substituted aminoarsines to determine the bonding site selectivity of BX_3 toward the As-N bond, study substituent effects on bonding site, investigate the chemical dynamics of bond dissociation/formation processes in solution, and attempt to isolate and characterise stable adducts.

Experimental

Standard high-vacuum line techniques and a Vacuum Atmospheres Model HE-43 Dri-Lab equipped with a Model HE-493 Dri-Train were used throughout for the handling of all compounds. (Dimethylamino)dimethylarsine (b.p. $74^\circ/108$ mm) was synthesised by the reaction of Me_2AsCl with excess $\text{Me}_2\text{NH}^{15}$ and was purified prior to use. (Dimethylamino)dichloroarsine (b.p. $75^\circ/25$ mm) was synthesised by the reaction of AsCl_3 with a stoichiometric amount of $(\text{Me}_2\text{N})_2\text{As}^{16}$. Me_2NBCl_2 was synthesised by the reaction of BCl_3 with $\text{Me}_2\text{NH}^{17,18}$ and was purified by trap-to-trap distillation prior to use. ^{11}B , ^{13}C and ^1H nmr spectra were recorded on a Nicolet 300 MHz Multinuclear FT nmr spectrometer operating at 96.3, 75.4 and 300.1 MHz, respectively. Chemical shift values for the ^{11}B resonance signals were measured relative to the signal of $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{OEt}_2$, high field shift being taken as negative. The ^1H and ^{13}C nmr chemical shifts were measured with respect to TMS as an internal reference.

Reaction of BCl_3 with Me_2NAsCl_2 and Me_2AsNMe_2 : Toluene- d_8 (2.5 ml) and Me_2NAsCl_2 or Me_2AsNMe_2 (1.0 mmol) were placed in the nmr reaction tube (12 mm \times 22.5 cm, Pyrex; equipped with a greaseless vacuum stopcock). The tube was evacuated at -196° and BCl_3 (1.0 mmol) condensed into it. The tube was warmed to -110° in a cyclohexene/liquid N_2 slush and then inserted into the precooled (-100°) probe of the nmr spectrometer. The ^{13}C , ^{11}B , and 1H nmr spectra of the reaction solution were recorded from -100 to 25° . The nmr spectral data are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 for the respective reactions.

Reaction of Me_2NBCl_2 with Me_2AsNMe_2 : Me_2NBCl_2 (1.0 mmol) and toluene- d_8 (2.5 ml) were placed in the nmr reaction tube (12 mm \times 22.5 cm, Pyrex; equipped with a greaseless vacuum stopcock). The tube was evacuated at -196° . Me_2AsNMe_2 (1.0 mmol) was condensed into it and the tube was sealed. The tube was agitated gently at -90° to assure mixing of reactants and then inserted into the precooled (-90°) probe of the spectrometer. The nmr spectra of the reaction solution were recorded from (-50 to 25°).

Acknowledgement

We are pleased to acknowledge the support of this research through the University College Committee on Faculty Research Grants at the University of Alabama at Birmingham. We also acknowledge the invitation of the Indian Chemical

Society to present this work during the 21st Annual Convention of Chemists.

References

1. Portion of a presentation at the Indian Chemical Society Annual Convention, Frontiers of Inorganic Chemistry Symposium, Calcutta, India, October 14-19, 1984.
2. G. W. PARSHALL in "The Chemistry of Boron and Its Compounds", ed. E. L. MUELTERTIUS, John Wiley, New York, 1967.
3. K. NIRDENZU and J. W. DAWSON in "The Chemistry of Boron and Its Compounds", ed. E. L. MUELTERTIUS, John Wiley, New York, 1967.
4. R. P. HOLMES and R. P. WAGNER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 357.
5. G. JUGIE, J. P. LAUSSAC and J. P. LAURENT, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3455.
6. B. RAPP and J. E. DRAKE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 2868.
7. S. FLEMING and R. W. PARRY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 1.
8. J. G. MORSE and K. W. MORSE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 2119.
9. M. L. DENNISTON and D. R. MARTIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 2175.
10. D. C. MENTE, J. L. MILLS and R. E. MITCHELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 123.
11. JOHN E. DRAKE, J. L. HENCHER and B. RAPP, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 2289.
12. J. APPEL and J. GROBE, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1979, **453**, 28.
13. R. BOHRA and H. W. ROESKY, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1984, **28**, 203.
14. F. H. WESTHEIMER, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1968, **1**, 70.
15. K. MODRITZER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, **92**, 2637.
16. H. J. VETTER and H. NOTH, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1964, **330**, 233.
17. C. A. BROWN and R. C. OSTHOFF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 2840.
18. E. WIBERG and K. SCHUSTER, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1933, **213**, 77.